

Metallic Complexes of 1-Thiocarbamido-3-Methyl Pyrazolone-5

S. N. PODDAR, S. GHOSH and A. K. DAS

Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta—700 032

Manuscript received 6 April 1976 ; accepted 15 June 1976.

The chelating ability of 1-thiocarbamido-3-methyl pyrazolone-5 has been described. It acts as a bidentate chelating agent and a number of complexes with Co(II), Co(III), Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), VO(II) and Cr(III) have been synthesized. The probable structures of these complexes have been suggested from the results of various physico-chemical measurements like molar conductance, visible and i.r. spectra, magnetic moment values etc. The compounds are usually associated with water molecules, which are present either as co-ordinated water or as lattice water. Octahedral stereochemistry has been suggested for all the complexes, excepting the anhydrous Ni(II) complex, which is supposed to possess a tetrahedral geometry. Of the tautomeric forms of the ligand existing in solution, it has been shown that the *enol* form enters into the complexation reactions.

THE chemistry of pyrazole and its derivatives has recently received considerable attention of coordination chemists by virtue of their applicability as potential complexing agents. Although pyrazole itself and its various alkyl— or aryl—derivatives are essentially weak bases, they act as monodentate coordinating ligands to form complexes with a number of metal ions, especially of the transitional series, and a number of publications has since been made on this subject^{1,2}. The potentiality of the pyrazoles as complex formers can be increased manifold by suitable substitution in the ring, when the resultant compounds function as multidentate ligands³. Thus antipyrine (1-phenyl 2, 3 dimethyl pyrazolone-5), and iso-propyl antipyrine, pyrimidone (4-dimethylamino-antipyrine) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone 5 have been widely mentioned in literature as reagents for detection and determination of various cations and anions.⁴ Poddar and co-workers⁵ investigated the metallation reactions of the compounds obtained by suitable substitution in the 1-position of the pyrazolone ring. Recently,

Snavely *et. al.*⁶⁻⁸ have studied the physico-chemical properties of the metallic derivatives of aryl-azo pyrazolones.

In the present communication, a substituted pyrazolone, *viz.* 1-thiocarbamido-3-methyl pyrazolone-5, has been used as a chelating agent for the complexation of some transition metal ions. The ligand functions as a bidentate monoprotic complexing agent and forms stable six-membered chelate rings with the metal ions used.

The resultant complexes can be represented by the general formula $ML_3 \cdot xSH_2O$ where M is Co(II), VO(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Fe(II) and X varies from 0 to 2; and $ML_3 \cdot yH_2O$ where M is Co(III), Cr(III), and y is either 3 or 4. The elemental analysis of the complexes together with the colours and magnetic moment values are shown in the Table I.

TABLE—1

Complex	Colour	Metal %		Nitrogen %		Water %		Magnetic Moment Values at 30°
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
Co(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Brown	10.13	10.09	21.85	21.58	9.17	9.25	Diamag.
Co(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Yellow	15.11	15.07	21.99	21.49	4.5	4.6	4.2 B. M.
Ni(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Green	14.84	14.64	20.21	20.05	9.4	8.9	2.9 B. M.
Ni(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂	Violet	15.80	15.75	22.00	22.50	—	—	3.05 B. M.
Cu(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Olive Green	15.69	15.36	21.01	20.31	8.5	8.7	1.7 B. M.
VO(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Yellowish Green	12.13	13.27	20.79	20.20	7.73	8.62	1.29 B. M.
Fe(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Cream	14.82	14.39	21.60	21.66	4.81	4.64	5.4 B. M.
Cr(C ₅ H ₇ ON ₂ S) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	Green	8.69	8.74	21.58	21.18	11.84	12.10	3.4 B. M.

Material and Methods.

The ligand has been synthesised by the condensation of equimolar amounts of ethyl-acetoacetate and thio-semicarbazide hydrochloride, according to the method described earlier⁵.

The pure product was obtained as white needle-shaped crystals melting at 180° by crystallisation from ethanol. Visible spectra in methanol solutions were recorded in a "SPECTROMOM-20" (Hungarian) instrument. The conductance values were recorded in a Philips P R 9500 conductivity bridge. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance calibrated with Hg [Co(CNS)₄].

Preparation of the complexes.

The hydrated Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II) and VO(II) complexes were prepared by mixing aqueous solution of the Na-salt of the ligand with the aqueous solution of the metal chlorides in 2:1 molar proportion and warming the mixture on waterbath for 15 to 30 min., when the metallic complexes separated out. The Cu(II) complex was obtained as above by adding a slight excess of sodium acetate to the mixture. The anhydrous Ni(II) complex was obtained by mixing the ligand solution with the metal salt solution in the ratio 2:1 together with two molar proportions of caustic soda solution. The mixture was digested on a waterbath, when the anhydrous Ni(II) complex separated out. The Co(III) complex was prepared from Co [(NH₃)₆]Cl₃ and the Cr(III) complex from [Cr(urea)₆]Cl₃·3H₂O by adding three molar proportions of the ligand and digesting the mixtures on water bath after making them alkaline with caustic soda solution. The complexes were filtered under suction, washed first with water and then with ethanol and finally dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

Conductance values of the Co(II), Cu(II), VO(II), Fe(II) and Cr(III) complexes in methanol solutions show that they are non-electrolytes.

Co(III) complex: The dark brown compound is diamagnetic. Its mull spectra show the bands at 26,500 cm⁻¹ and at 21,000 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} and ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{1g} transitions respectively. The second band is splitted into two components. It is suggested that the Co(III) complex possesses an octahedral stereochemistry^{9,10}.

Co(II) complex: The light yellow bis-aquo Co(II) complex has a magnetic moment value of 4.2 B.M. and its electronic spectrum in methanol solution consists of two bands, one at 19,000 cm⁻¹ and the other at 16,200 cm⁻¹. The two bands correspond to the ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g}(F) octahedral transitions respectively. The assignment of the band at 16,200 cm⁻¹ is, however, tentative¹¹. Since the complex in solution may possess a distorted octahedral geometry with coordinated water and a solvent molecule, the first and the second transitions can be assigned as ν₃ and ν₂ bands.

Ni(II) complexes: The bis-aquo light green Ni(II) complex has the magnetic moment value of 2.9 B.M. Its mull spectra consists of three bands in the regions 15,600 cm⁻¹, 13,000 cm⁻¹ and 9,600 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the transitions ³A_{2g}→¹E_{1g}(D) (spin-forbidden), ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}(F) respectively. The second and the third transition can be assigned as ν₂ and ν₁ bands. The higher frequency ν₃ band probably occurs in the u.v. region and as such could not be detected in the spectrum in the visible region⁹.

The anhydrous violet Ni(II) complex has a magnetic moment value of 3.05 B.M. The mull spectrum consists of four bands at 19,000 cm⁻¹, 13,500 cm⁻¹, 11,300 cm⁻¹ and 9,000 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the transitions ³T_{1g}→¹T_{2g}, ³T_{1g}→³T_{1g}(P), ³T_{1g}→¹E and ³T_{1g}→³A_{2g} respectively. The second and the fourth bands can be assigned as the ν₃ and ν₂ bands. The spectrum suggests a tetrahedral stereochemistry for the anhydrous violet Ni(II) complex¹².

Cu(II) complex: The olive-green bis-aquo Cu(II) complex has the spectrum consisting of a single broad envelope around 14,500 cm⁻¹, which is slightly splitted up into two components as is observed in many cases of copper(II) complexes¹³. This, together with the magnetic moment value of 1.7 B.M. of the compound, is suggestive of an octahedral stereochemistry for the complex.

VO(II) complex: The light green bis-aquo VO(II) complex has a magnetic moment value of 1.29 B.M. The electronic spectrum of the complex in methanol solution consists of a band at 14,000 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at 16,000 cm⁻¹. The band at 14,000 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the ²B₂→²E₁ transition, whereas the shoulder at 16,000 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the ²B₂→²B₁ transition, which is allowed vibronically and should appear in all polarizations¹⁴.

Fe(II) complex: The cream coloured di-hydrated Fe(II) complex has the magnetic moment value of 5.4 B.M. The solution spectrum in ethanol consists of two bands in the region of 19,500 cm⁻¹ and 8,000 cm⁻¹. The first band is probably of charge transfer origin, whereas the second one is attributed to the ⁵T_{2g}→⁵E_g transition as is usual for octahedral complexes of Fe(II).^{15,16}

Cr(III) complex: The Cr(III) complex is dirty green in colour. The solution in ethanol exhibits two bands at 17,600 cm⁻¹, and at 15,000 cm⁻¹ which correspond to the transitions ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{2g}(F) and ⁴A_{2g}→²E_g respectively. The spectral nature together with the magnetic moment value of 3.4 B.M. of the complex point towards its octahedral geometry⁹.

I. R. spectral data: The infra-red spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in chloroform solution or in nujol. The i.r. spectrum of the ligand consists, among others, a number of bands in the region 3460–3000 cm⁻¹, which are due to the –NH₂ stretching frequencies of the thiocarbamido group. Under

9. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 5, 33.
10. A. B. P. LEVER in "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1968, p. 314.
11. A. B. P. LEVER in "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1968, p. 319.
12. M. GOODGAME, D. M. L. GOOGAME and F. A. COTTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4161.
13. A. B. P. LEVER in "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1968, p. 356.
14. G. J. BALLHAUSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.
15. K. MADEJA and E. KONIG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, 25, 377.
16. A. B. P. LEVER in "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1968, p. 300.
17. D. R. P. KNORR, *Ann.*, 1887, 238 137.
18. D. R. P. KNORR, *Ann.*, 1896, 293, 1.
19. J. KITAMURA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1940, 60, 45.